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ON THE SOUND FIELD STRUCTURE OF ROTOR-STATOR INTERACTION NOISE

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ABSTRACT

The paper gives an analytical study to elucidate the logical mechanism underlying the complex parameter dependence of the rotor-stator interaction noise. The sound field is resolved into component sound fields originating from individual Fourier modes of the rotor wake upwash velocity distribution on the stator vanes. The difference in the parametric dependence of the phase among the component sound fields is a key factor. It was made clear that superposition of the component sound fields can be constructive or destructive and a small change of a parameter can result in a significant change of the noise level.

Stepwise construction of the rotor-stator interaction sound field in the process of back and forth propagation of the sound waves between the rotor and stator was also studied.

INTRODUCTION

It is the common understanding that the main source of the tone noise of ducted fan engines operating at subsonic rotor tip speeds is impingement of wakes coming from upstream rotor blades on downstream stator vanes. The unsteady pressure fluctuations on the vane surfaces resulting from the wake impingement become the principal sound source. The sound waves generated from the stator vanes propagate and inevitably interact with the rotor blades. The sound waves reflected at the rotor blades again interact with stator vanes, and such back-and-forth interaction events repeat infinite times. We should note that the acoustic interaction between the rotor and the stator in relative motion is neither a simple reflection nor a simple transmission, but scatterings of sound modes and frequencies take place at each interaction. Then, there arises a problem: how much and in what manner the sound power emitted from the engine is modified by the rotor-stator acoustic interaction.

To explore the problem, it will be useful to investigate the process of sound field construction. There is no experimental way, however, to study the problem by comparing the states with and without the rotor-stator acoustic interaction.

Nowadays, CFD and CAA are fully established as the standard tools for studies in fluid mechanics and aeroacoustics. They are indispensable for highly accurate prediction of physical quantities of realistic models involving a number of parameters and variables.

However, the CFD and CAA computations need long computation time for extensive parametric studies. So, they are inconvenient for causality analysis, where effectiveness of individual factors is evaluated by conducting computation with systematic change of input values of parameters.

On the other hand, classical analytical methods can only deal with simplified models restricted by many assumptions. However, the explicit solution forms themselves are very useful because they can give meaningful information of causality relationship. Moreover, classical analytical methods enable us to conduct extensive parametric studies with very low computation cost.

Therefore, the author believes that classical mathematical methods still keep a good standing as useful tools to tackle the problem of logical understanding of the mechanism.

The paper gives the mathematical analysis based on the unsteady lifting surface theory developed by the author for the rotor-stator model shown in Fig. 1. The details of the mathematical formulations are described in e.g. Ref. [1].

Calculations based on the theory indicate that the tone noise field resulting from interaction of the stator vanes with the oncoming rotor wakes is extensively modified by rotor-stator acoustic interaction, and small changes in design parameters can give rise to drastic changes of the sound power level. However, logical mechanism underlying complicated and sensitive parametric dependence has not been made clear, yet.

This paper aims, firstly, at making clear the mechanism giving rise to the periodic variation of the sound power with the rotor-stator distance, and secondly, at investigating the process of the sound field construction by the rotor-stator acoustic interaction.

NOMENCLATURE

All quantities are made dimensionless with respect to

length R^* = outer duct wall radius
velocity W_a^* = mean axial flow velocity
density ρ_0^* = mean fluid density
pressure $\rho_0^* W_a^{*2}$
time R^*/W_a^*

Further the following notations are used:

C_{aR} axial chord length of rotor
 C_{aS} axial chord length of stator
 $EM_{\pm}(\nu, \mu, \ell)$ modal sound power: Eq. (23)
 $EC_{\pm}(\nu, \mu)$ wave number component of sound power:
Eq. (24)
 $E_{\pm}(\nu)$ frequency component of sound power: Eq. (25)
 $FP_{\pm}(\nu, \mu, \ell)$ modal pressure amplitude: Eq. (20)
 G distance between mid-chords of rotor and stator
 h hub-to-tip ratio
 M_a mean axial flow Mach number
 N_R rotor blade count
 N_S stator vane count
 R duct radius (=1)
 (r, θ, z) cylindrical coordinate system in the duct frame of
reference
 t time
 $\Delta p_{R,\nu}(r, z)$ unsteady pressure difference across a rotor
blade surface at frequency $\nu N_S \Omega$: Eq. (15)
 $\Delta p_{S,\nu}(r, z)$ unsteady pressure difference across a stator
vane surface at frequency $\nu N_R \Omega$: Eq. (15)
 Ω peripheral rotor tip speed normalized by mean axial
flow velocity
Subscript
+ downstream from the stator
- upstream from the rotor

Fig. 1. Fan-stage model. The rotor rotation velocity Ω is positive, when the rotation is clockwise looked from downstream.

MATHEMATICAL METHODS

General Formulation

The paper deals with a model composed of a rotor and a stator in an annular duct of infinite axial extent with an outer radius R^* and a hub-to-tip ratio h (Fig. 1). The fluid is an inviscid nonconducting perfect gas. The

undisturbed flow is of a subsonic uniform axial flow of an axial velocity W_a^* , a density ρ_0^* and an axial Mach number M_a . Unstarred symbols used hereafter are dimensionless as described in nomenclature. The rotor blades and the stator vanes are assumed of no thickness, of no axial sweep, of no peripheral lean and of no steady loading. The flow disturbances are assumed to originate from the rotor wakes and to be very small.

To begin with, let the mathematical formulations of the theory be described symbolically.

We express the aerodynamic unsteady loading on the rotor blades \mathbf{P}_R composed of components $\Delta p_{R,\mu}$ of the stator vane passing frequency and its harmonics $\mu N_S \Omega$: $\mu = \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$, and the aerodynamic unsteady loading on the stator vanes \mathbf{P}_S composed of components $\Delta p_{S,\nu}$ of the rotor blade passing frequency and its harmonics $\nu N_R \Omega$: $\nu = \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P}_R &= \left[\dots, \Delta p_{R,-2}, \Delta p_{R,-1}, \Delta p_{R,+1}, \Delta p_{R,+2}, \dots \right]^T \\ \mathbf{P}_S &= \left[\dots, \Delta p_{S,-2}, \Delta p_{S,-1}, \Delta p_{S,+1}, \Delta p_{S,+2}, \dots \right]^T \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The disturbance flow must satisfy the flow tangency condition on the surfaces of the rotor blades and the stator vanes expressed as simultaneous integral equations for the blade and vane loadings given by Eqs. (17) and (18). Here, we express the equations in compact form:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{R \leftarrow R} & \mathbf{K}_{R \leftarrow S} \\ \mathbf{K}_{S \leftarrow R} & \mathbf{K}_{S \leftarrow S} \end{bmatrix} * \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{P}_R \\ \mathbf{P}_S \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ -\mathbf{W} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Here, $\mathbf{K}_{R \leftarrow R}$, $\mathbf{K}_{R \leftarrow S}$, etc. are matrices of velocity kernel functions. Further, for instance, $\mathbf{K}_{R \leftarrow S} * \mathbf{P}_S$ denotes convolution of kernel function $\mathbf{K}_{R \leftarrow S}$ and loading function \mathbf{P}_S , which gives upwash velocity on a rotor blade surface induced by the stator loading \mathbf{P}_S .

Further,

$$\mathbf{W} = \left[\dots, W_{\perp S,-2}, W_{\perp S,-1}, W_{\perp S,+1}, W_{\perp S,+2}, \dots \right]^T \quad (3)$$

gives Fourier components of the rotor wake upwash velocity on the stator vanes $W_{\perp S,\lambda}$ of circumferential wave number λN_R : $\lambda = \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$. We apply the wake model used in Ref. [2]. Figure 2 shows distributions of the upwash velocity and its Fourier components along a stator axial chord-line. We should note that Fourier component of order λ is equivalent to a sinusoidal gust of axial wave length $2\pi / (\lambda N_R \Omega)$ and gust frequency $\lambda N_R \Omega$.

Here it should be pointed out that the diagonal elements $\mathbf{K}_{R \leftarrow R}$ and $\mathbf{K}_{S \leftarrow S}$ are diagonal matrices, which do not give rise to frequency scattering. On the other hand, the off-diagonal elements $\mathbf{K}_{S \leftarrow R}$ and $\mathbf{K}_{R \leftarrow S}$ denote rotor-stator acoustic interaction, and they themselves are matrices with non-zero off-diagonal elements giving rise to frequency scattering.

Fig. 2. Rotor wake upwash velocity normalized by the axial flow velocity around the stator row. The original form $\Sigma\lambda$ and Fourier components of circumferential wave number λN_R : $\lambda = 1, 2, 3, 4$ and 5 .

Resolution of Sound Field into Components Caused by Individual Fourier Component of the Wakes

Consider the case of interaction with a single sinusoidal gust component of order λ :

$$\mathbf{W}^{(\lambda)} = [\dots, 0, W_{\perp S, -\lambda}, 0, \dots, 0, W_{\perp S, +\lambda}, 0, \dots]^T \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{R \leftarrow R} & \mathbf{K}_{R \leftarrow S} \\ \mathbf{K}_{S \leftarrow R} & \mathbf{K}_{S \leftarrow S} \end{bmatrix} * \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{P}_R^{(\lambda)} \\ \mathbf{P}_S^{(\lambda)} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ -\mathbf{W}^{(\lambda)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Under the rotor-stator acoustic interaction the sound pressure field $\mathbf{P}^{(\lambda)}$ originating from a single Fourier component is composed of not only the gust frequency component $\lambda N_R \Omega$ but also all other harmonic frequency components $\nu N_R \Omega$: $\nu \neq \lambda$.

We should note that the sound field originating from individual sinusoidal gust components are independent of each other, and the general sound field generated from the full rotor wake configuration is constructed by linear superposition:

$$\mathbf{P} = \sum_{\lambda=-\infty}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}^{(\lambda)}, \mathbf{P}_R = \sum_{\lambda=-\infty}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_R^{(\lambda)}, \mathbf{P}_S = \sum_{\lambda=-\infty}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_S^{(\lambda)} \quad (6)$$

We express the general acoustic power of the synthesized sound field and the acoustic power of the component sound field originating from individual sinusoidal gust component by $E_{\pm}(\nu)$ and $E_{\pm}^{(\lambda)}(\nu)$, respectively. Here ν denotes the harmonic order of the frequency $\nu N_R \Omega$ and subscripts + and - denote downstream region from the stator and upstream region from the rotor, respectively.

Analysis of Rotor-Stator Acoustic Interaction Process

Solution of simultaneous equation system (2) or (5) provides the state resulting from infinite number of sound wave reflections and interactions at the both blade rows. To obtain a deep insight into the construction of the sound field, it will be very helpful to trace the interaction process step by step. Analysis of the step by step interaction process can be conducted by the algorithm shown below.

We express increments in the loadings of the rotor blades and the stator vanes at the event of Step n by $\delta \mathbf{P}_{R,(n)}$ and $\delta \mathbf{P}_{S,(n)}$, respectively. Further, express the

loadings of the rotor blades and the stator vanes when the interaction process is advanced up to Step n by $\mathbf{P}_{R,(n)}$ and $\mathbf{P}_{S,(n)}$, respectively. Then we have

$$\mathbf{P}_{R,(n)} = \sum_{k=0}^n \delta \mathbf{P}_{R,(k)}, \mathbf{P}_{S,(n)} = \sum_{k=0}^n \delta \mathbf{P}_{S,(k)} \quad (7)$$

The increments at each Step are calculated as follows:

Step 0: Rotor wakes impinge on the stator vanes and create the vane loading $\delta \mathbf{P}_{S,(0)}$, which generates sound waves.

$$\mathbf{K}_{S \leftarrow S} * \delta \mathbf{P}_{S,(0)} = -\mathbf{W}, \delta \mathbf{P}_{R,(0)} = \mathbf{0} \quad (8)$$

Fig. 3. State at step 0. $\mathbf{P}_{R,(0)} = \mathbf{0}$, $\mathbf{P}_{S,(0)} = \delta \mathbf{P}_{S,(0)}$

Step 1: Sound waves generated by the stator vane loading $\delta \mathbf{P}_{S,(0)}$ interact with the rotor blades creating blade loading $\delta \mathbf{P}_{R,(1)}$, which generates additional sound waves.

$$\mathbf{K}_{R \leftarrow R} * \delta \mathbf{P}_{R,(1)} = -\mathbf{K}_{R \leftarrow S} * \delta \mathbf{P}_{S,(0)}, \delta \mathbf{P}_{S,(1)} = \mathbf{0} \quad (9)$$

Fig. 4. State at step 1. $\mathbf{P}_{R,(1)} = \delta \mathbf{P}_{R,(1)}$, $\mathbf{P}_{S,(1)} = \delta \mathbf{P}_{S,(0)}$

Step 2: Sound waves generated by the rotor blade loading $\delta \mathbf{P}_{R,(1)}$ interact with the stator vanes creating incremental vane loading $\delta \mathbf{P}_{S,(2)}$, which generates additional sound waves.

$$\mathbf{K}_{S \rightarrow S} * \delta \mathbf{P}_{S,(2)} = -\mathbf{K}_{S \leftarrow R} * \delta \mathbf{P}_{R,(1)}, \delta \mathbf{P}_{R,(2)} = \mathbf{0} \quad (10)$$

Fig. 5. State at step 2. $\mathbf{P}_{R,(2)} = \delta \mathbf{P}_{R,(1)}$, $\mathbf{P}_{S,(2)} = \delta \mathbf{P}_{S,(0)} + \delta \mathbf{P}_{S,(2)}$

Step 3: Sound waves generated by the stator vane loading $\delta \mathbf{P}_{S,(2)}$ interact with the rotor blades, creating incremental blade loading $\delta \mathbf{P}_{R,(3)}$, which generates additional sound waves.

$$\mathbf{K}_{R \leftarrow R} * \delta \mathbf{P}_{R,(3)} = -\mathbf{K}_{R \leftarrow S} * \delta \mathbf{P}_{S,(2)}, \delta \mathbf{P}_{S,(3)} = \mathbf{0} \quad (11)$$

Fig. 6. State at step 3.

$$\mathbf{P}_{R,(3)} = \delta \mathbf{P}_{R,(1)} + \delta \mathbf{P}_{R,(3)}, \mathbf{P}_{S,(3)} = \delta \mathbf{P}_{S,(0)} + \delta \mathbf{P}_{S,(2)}$$

To summarize, the increment components at each interaction step are determined by successively solving the individual interaction equation step by step.

$$\text{Step } n = 0: \mathbf{K}_{S \leftarrow S} * \delta \mathbf{P}_{S,(0)} = -\mathbf{W}, \quad \delta \mathbf{P}_{R,(0)} = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \text{Step } n = \text{odd}: \quad & \mathbf{K}_{R \leftarrow R} * \delta \mathbf{P}_{R,(n)} = -\mathbf{K}_{R \leftarrow S} * \delta \mathbf{P}_{S,(n-1)}, \\ & \delta \mathbf{P}_{R,(n-1)} = \mathbf{0} \\ \text{Step } n = \text{even}: \quad & \mathbf{K}_{S \leftarrow S} * \delta \mathbf{P}_{S,(n)} = -\mathbf{K}_{S \leftarrow R} * \delta \mathbf{P}_{R,(n-1)}, \\ & \delta \mathbf{P}_{S,(n-1)} = \mathbf{0} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (13)$$

Stepwise tracing the interaction process is the forte of the mathematical analysis, and experiments or CFD computations are unable to do such a task.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Resolution Analysis

In the example computations given hereafter, the design parameters are specified as follows. The hub-to-tip ratio $h = 0.5$, the rotor blade count $N_R = 20$, the stator vane count $N_S = 30$, the rotor tip speed normalized by the axial flow velocity $\Omega = 2.089$, and the axial Mach number $M_a = 0.3$. The cut-on duct modes in this condition are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Cut-on modes up to the third harmonic blade passing frequency $\nu = 3$. Frequency = $\nu N_R \Omega$. Circumferential wave number $n = \nu N_R + \mu N_S$. Radial mode number ℓ .

ν	μ	ℓ	n
1	-1	0	-10
2	-1	0,1,2,3	10
2	2	0	-20
3	-1	0,1	30
3	-2	0,1,2,3,4,5,6	0
3	-3	0,1	-30

Fig. 7. Sound pressure waves of the fundamental blade passing frequency and circumferential wave number $n = -10$ on the outer wall surface.

Figure 7 demonstrates the sound pressure waves of the fundamental blade passing frequency $\nu = 1$ on the outer wall surface. Here, only a mode of circumferential wave number $n = -10$ is cut-on. We can observe that upstream propagation of sound waves is effectively blocked by the rotor.

Fig. 8. Variations of downstream acoustic power $E_+(\nu)$ with the rotor-stator distance. Frequency $\nu N_R \Omega$: $\nu = 1, 2$ and 3 . Solid lines denote the condition of full rotor-stator acoustic coupling, whereas dash lines denote the condition of acoustically decoupled rotor and stator.

Fig. 9. Variations of upstream acoustic power $E_-(\nu)$ with the rotor-stator distance. Frequency $\nu N_R \Omega$: $\nu = 1, 2$ and 3 . Solid lines denote the condition of full rotor-stator acoustic coupling, whereas dash lines denote the condition of acoustically decoupled rotor and stator.

Figures 8 and 9 show variations of the sound power of tone noise propagating downstream from the stator and upstream from the rotor, respectively, dependent upon the rotor-stator distance. Dash lines denote the case of step 0 (acoustically decoupled rotor and stator), whereas solid lines denote the case of step full (full rotor-stator acoustic coupling).

The influence of the rotor-stator acoustic interaction (difference between dash lines and solid lines) is rather minor for the downstream sound power (Fig. 8). However, it is well worth noting that the rotor-stator acoustic interaction is likely to increase the downstream acoustic power.

On the other hand, the influence of the rotor-stator acoustic interaction is highly significant for the upstream sound power (Fig. 9). Here, we can see two striking features.

- Firstly, the sound power under rotor-stator acoustic interaction is very much lower than that (decoupled) without the rotor-stator acoustic interaction. Attention should be paid to difference in scale of vertical coordinate between Fig. 8 and Fig. 9.
- Secondly, the sound power under rotor-stator acoustic interaction varies nearly periodically with the rotor-stator distance. The difference between the maximum and minimum values is very large, and in some cases the difference is higher than 10 dB.

The reason of the first matter is obvious. The cut-on duct modes propagating upstream and spinning in the direction opposite to the rotor rotation have wave fronts nearly parallel to the rotor blade surfaces, and they are largely reflected at the blade surfaces and less transmitted through the rotor blade row. In particular in the case of the present example the sound waves at the fundamental blade passing frequency ($\nu=1$) are composed of only a single cut-on duct mode of circumferential wave number $n=-10$ and radial mode order $\ell=0$ which is spinning counter to the rotor rotation. Therefore, as shown in Fig. 7, they are mostly reflected at the rotor blade surfaces and the sound power upstream becomes very small. On the other hand, as shown in Table 1, the sound waves of the second and the third harmonic blade passing frequencies ($\nu=2$ and $\nu=3$) are composed of not only cut-on modes spinning counter to the rotor rotation ($n<0$) but also those spinning in the same direction as the rotor rotation ($n>0$) which are more transmissible through the rotor.

Fig. 10. Real part of complex amplitude of unsteady aerodynamic loading distribution $\Delta p_{s,\nu}(r,z)$ on a stator vane. Contributions of individual wake Fourier components $\lambda=1,2,$ and 3 and complete wake $\Sigma\lambda$. Frequency= $\nu N_R\Omega$: $\nu=3$. $G/R=0.64$

Fig. 11. Real part of complex amplitude of unsteady aerodynamic loading distribution $\Delta p_{R,\mu}(r,z)$ on a rotor blade. Contributions of individual wake Fourier components $\lambda=1$ and 3 and complete wake $\Sigma\lambda$. Frequency= $\mu N_s\Omega$: $\mu=1$. $G/R=0.64$

Therefore, the reductions of the sound powers of higher harmonic frequencies by the rotor-stator acoustic interaction are less significant than the reduction of the fundamental frequency sound power.

To elucidate the mechanism giving rise to the periodic dependence of the acoustic powers on the rotor-stator distance is a core subject of the present paper. Recall that each Fourier component of the rotor wake gives multiple frequency components of unsteady blade and vane loadings and generate multiple frequency components of sound waves.

Figures 10 and 11 show contributions of individual wake Fourier components and the complete wake to the unsteady loadings on a stator vane and a rotor blade, respectively. Figure 10 indicates that the unsteady loading on the stator vanes at frequency $\nu N_R\Omega$ is overwhelmingly dominated by contribution of wake Fourier component of $\lambda=\nu$. However, as Fig. 11 shows, individual Fourier components of the rotor wake make contributions of same order of magnitude to the unsteady loading on the rotor blades.

Figure 12 shows variations of upstream acoustic powers $E_-(\nu)$ and $E_-^{(\lambda)}(\nu)$: $\lambda=1,2,3$ and 4 at the fundamental blade passing frequency $\nu N_R\Omega$: $\nu=1$ with the distance between the rotor and the stator. We can observe three distinguishing features.

- As to the acoustic power components $E_-^{(\lambda)}(\nu)$, the component $\lambda=1$ (originating from the wake Fourier component of the blade passing frequency $\lambda=\nu=1$) is most dominant, but the second highest component $\lambda=3$ is never very small.
- Individual acoustic power components $E_-^{(\lambda)}(\nu)$ rather monotonously varies with the rotor-stator distance.
- The general acoustic power $E_-(\nu)$ shows distinctive periodic variation with the rotor-stator distance.

Fig. 12. Variations of upstream acoustic powers of the fundamental blade passing frequency $\nu=1$ with the rotor-stator axial distance originating from individual sinusoidal wake gust components $\lambda=1,2,3$ and 4 and the original full wake $\Sigma\lambda$

Here, we should recall again that the sound waves originating from the full wakes are constructed by linear superposition of the sound waves originating from individual Fourier components of the wakes. Then, the last point suggests that the superposition of the sound waves can be constructive (in phase) or destructive (out of phase) and the condition will be dependent upon the rotor-stator distance. In order to verify the inference, we investigate the situation of duct mode superposition.

The duct modes of the present system are identified by the frequency $\nu N_R \Omega$ in the duct frame of reference, the circumferential wave number $n = \nu N_R + \mu N_S$, and the radial mode order ℓ , and we denote the mode parameters by notation (ν, μ, ℓ) . We express the complex modal pressure amplitude by $FP_{\pm}(\nu, \mu, \ell)$ for the general sound field and $FP_{\pm}^{(\lambda)}(\nu, \mu, \ell)$ for the component sound field originating from the individual sinusoidal gust component. Then, we have also

$$FP_{\pm}(\nu, \mu, \ell) = \sum_{\lambda=-\infty}^{\infty} FP_{\pm}^{(\lambda)}(\nu, \mu, \ell) \quad (14)$$

In the present example computation, we have only one cut-on mode $(\pm 1, \mp 1, 0)$ for the fundamental blade passing frequency $\nu = \pm 1$. Figure 13 shows variations of the phase angles of the complex modal pressure amplitudes $FP_{-}^{(1)}(1, -1, 0)$ and $FP_{-}^{(3)}(1, -1, 0)$ with the rotor-stator distance. We can see that the phases change periodically, and the period of the component λ is inversely proportional to λ similarly to the axial wave length of the corresponding sinusoidal wake gust component (Fig. 2).

Comparison of Fig. 13 with Fig. 12 indicates that the local maximum points of the acoustic power correspond to in-phase condition of $\lambda=1$ and $\lambda=3$ components, whereas the local minimum points correspond to out-of-phase (by π) condition of the two components. Note that the in-phase condition occurs twice per period of the $\lambda=1$ component.

Fig. 13. Variation of the phase angles of the modal pressure amplitudes $FP_{-}^{(\lambda)}(1, -1, 0)$: $\lambda=1$ and 3 with the rotor-stator distance.

(a) $G/R=0.64$

(b) $G/R=0.67$

Fig. 14. Complex modal pressure amplitudes of $FP_{-}^{(\lambda)}(1, -1, 0)$: $\lambda=1, 2$ and 3 and $FP_{-}(1, -1, 0)$ denoted by $\Sigma\lambda$ at the rotor-stator distance (a) $G/R=0.64$ and (b) $G/R=0.67$

Fig. 15. Sound pressure distributions of the fundamental blade passing frequency on the outer wall surface in the region upstream from the rotor. Contributions originating from the rotor wake Fourier components $\lambda = 1$ and $\lambda = 3$ and the complete rotor wake $\Sigma\lambda$.

Figures 14 (a) and 14 (b) more clearly demonstrate the situation. Here the modal pressure amplitudes are shown in complex plane for $G/R = 0.64$ (nearly out-of-phase condition), and $G/R = 0.67$ (nearly in-phase condition), respectively. In Fig. 14 (a), the components $\lambda = 1$ and $\lambda = 3$ are nearly out-of-phase, and the synthesized modal amplitude becomes smaller. On the other hand, in Fig. 14 (b), $\lambda = 1$ and $\lambda = 3$ are nearly in-phase, and the synthesized modal amplitude becomes larger.

Figure 15 visualizes destructive superposition in the case of (a) $G/R=0.64$ and constructive superposition in the case of (b) $G/R=0.67$ of the sound waves originating from wake Fourier components $\lambda = 1$ and $\lambda = 3$ in the upstream region from the rotor.

Interaction Step Analysis

Next, let us investigate the process of the sound field construction by back and forth propagation of sound waves between the rotor and the stator.

First of all, we pay our attention to transition of the strength of the sound sources, i.e., the unsteady loadings on the stator vanes and the rotor blades.

Figure 16 shows complex amplitude of unsteady aerodynamic loading on a stator vane at step 0 (no rotor-stator acoustic interaction) and step full stages. Difference between the two stages is very small. In other words, the scale of velocity disturbance of sound waves is very small compared with that brought about by the rotor wakes, and hence the rotor-stator acoustic interaction gives only slight changes to the stator surface pressure distribution. It may be almost impossible to clearly discern by CFD computations.

Fig. 16. Complex amplitude of unsteady aerodynamic loading distribution $\Delta p_{S,v}(r, z)$ on a stator vane at step 0 and step full stages. Frequency = $\nu N_R \Omega$: $\nu = 1$. $G/R = 0.64$

Fig. 17. Complex amplitude of unsteady aerodynamic loading $\Delta p_{R,\mu}(r, z)$ on a rotor blade at step 1 and step full stages. Frequency = $\mu N_S \Omega$: $\mu = 1$. $G/R = 0.64$

On the other hand, we have no unsteady loading on the rotor blades at step 0 stage, and unsteady loading on the rotor blades is solely produced by interaction of the blades with sound waves coming from the stator vanes. Figure 17 shows unsteady loading distributions on a rotor blade surface at step 1 and step full stages.

First of all, we can observe that unsteady loadings on the rotor blades are far smaller (by factor of one-tenth lower) than those on the stator vanes. As noted above, the unsteady loading on the stator vanes at step 0 is generated by interaction of the stator vanes with vortical disturbances

of the rotor wakes, which are much larger than the sound wave disturbances.

Secondly, difference in the blade loading between step 1 and step full stages is very small. It implies that additional disturbances quickly become smaller as the interaction step advances.

However, we should note that from the stand point of human sensibility of noise, a change of sound pressure level brought about by a small change of unsteady loadings on the rotor blades and the stator vanes, i.e., virtual noise sources, can be of no little significance.

Fig. 18. Variation of downstream acoustic power of the fundamental blade passing frequency ($\nu=1$) with the rotor-stator distance. Dependence on the interaction step.

Fig. 19. Variation of upstream acoustic power of the fundamental blade passing frequency ($\nu=1$) with the rotor-stator distance. Dependence on the interaction step.

Figures 18 and 19 show downstream and upstream acoustic powers dependent on the rotor-stator acoustic interaction step, respectively. As Fig. 18 shows, acoustic waves downstream from the stator are less influenced by the rotor-stator acoustic interaction, and the state at step 2 is already very close to the state of full interaction.

On the other hand, the rotor-stator acoustic interaction is crucial to sound field upstream from the rotor, and interaction up to step 3 is necessary to establish nearly full interaction state.

Fig. 20. The modal acoustic power of upstream propagating wave number mode $EC_{-}^{(\lambda)}(\nu, \mu) : \nu=3, \mu=-2, n=0$. Frequency $\nu N_R \Omega : \nu=3$. Circumferential wave number $n = \nu N_R + \mu N_S = 0$. $G/R=0.67$

Fig. 21. The modal acoustic power of upstream propagating wave number mode $EC_{-}^{(\lambda)}(\nu, \mu) : \nu=3, \mu=-1, n=+30$. Frequency $\nu N_R \Omega : \nu=3$. Circumferential wave number $n = \nu N_R + \mu N_S = 30$. Spinning in the direction of the rotor rotation. $G/R=0.67$

Fig. 22. The modal acoustic power of upstream propagating wave number mode $EC_{-}^{(\lambda)}(\nu, \mu) : \nu=3, \mu=-3, n=-30$. Frequency $\nu N_R \Omega : \nu=3$. Circumferential wave number $n = \nu N_R + \mu N_S = -30$. Spinning counter to the rotor rotation. $G/R=0.67$

To summarize, twice interactions (step 0 and step 2) with the stator and twice interactions (step 1 and step 3) with the rotor can give nearly full interaction states of sound fields downstream from the stator and upstream from the rotor, respectively.

As Table 1 shows, the sound waves at the third

harmonic blade passing frequency $\nu = 3$ are composed of cut-on modes of circumferential wave numbers $n = -30, 0,$ and $+30$.

As Fig. 20 shows, the modes of $n=0$ are produced only by the sound wave interactions at the rotor blades (at step 1, 3, ...), and make only small contribution to the noise level. Pay attention to the scale of vertical coordinate. Note that the stator vanes of zero stagger angle and zero thickness can not generate sound waves of zero circumferential wave number, and hence, there exists no sound wave of $n=0$ at step 0. It is interesting that even orders of the wake Fourier components $\lambda = 2$ and $\lambda = 4$ are the main contributors.

On the other hand, at step 0 stage, modes of wave number $n=+30$ (spinning in the direction of rotor rotation) and $n=-30$ (spinning counter to the rotor rotation) are generated by interaction of wake Fourier component $\lambda = 3$ with the stator vanes. The sound powers of both modes are same at step 0 (before acoustic interaction with the rotor blades).

Fig. 23. Variations of frequency components of upstream sound power $E_{-}^{(\lambda)}(\nu): \nu=1,2,3$ with interaction steps originating from the wake Fourier component $\lambda = 3$. $G/R=0.67$

Fig. 24. Variations of frequency components of upstream sound power $E_{-}^{(\lambda)}(\nu): \nu=1,2,3$ with interaction steps originating from the wake Fourier component $\lambda = 2$. $G/R=0.67$

Fig. 25. Variations of frequency components of upstream sound power $E_{-}^{(\lambda)}(\nu): \nu=1,2,3$ with interaction steps originating from the wake Fourier component $\lambda = 1$. $G/R=0.67$

However, as Fig. 22 shows, upstream propagation of modes of $n=-30$ (with wave front nearly parallel to the rotor blade surface) is nearly completely blocked by the rotor, and the power level after interaction step 1 is quite low. On the other hand, as Fig. 21 shows, transmission of the modes of $n=+30$ (with wave front nearly normal to the rotor blade surface) through the rotor is only partially blocked. Moreover, we should rather note that contributions from other wake Fourier components ($\lambda \neq 3$) are never small, and consequently the total sound power ($\Sigma \lambda$) of $n=+30$ is rather enhanced at step 1.

The scatterings of modes and frequencies are prominent features of the rotor-stator acoustic interaction, and multiple frequency components are produced from each wake Fourier component. Figures 23, 24 and 25 show stepwise variations of frequency components of upstream sound power originating from a single wake Fourier component $\lambda = 3$, $\lambda = 2$ and $\lambda = 1$, respectively. Here, attention should be paid to the logarithmic scale of the vertical coordinate.

We can clearly see that scattering to frequency components other than $\nu \neq \lambda$ takes place at and after step 1. Further, it is worthy of attention that the tendency of sound energy transfer to higher harmonic frequency modes is stronger than that to lower harmonic frequency modes. This can be attributed to the fact that the higher the frequency is, the larger number of modes become cut-on.

CONCLUSIONS

The construction of the fan tone noise field caused by impingement of the rotor wakes on the downstream stator vanes was analyzed from the standpoint of superposition of component sound fields originating from interaction of the stator vanes with individual Fourier components of the rotor wakes. Mathematical analysis of tracing the state variation with stepwise interaction of sound waves between the rotor and the stator was also conducted.

It was made clear that the superposition of duct modes of the multiple component sound fields can be in-phase or out-of-phase resulting in significant change in the

synthesized sound power level.

The periodic variation of the sound power level with the rotor-stator distance is explained by the difference in phase between the components originating from individual wake Fourier components.

Twice interactions with the stator and twice interactions with the rotor are essentially enough to establish nearly full interaction states of the sound fields downstream and upstream, respectively.

The rotor-stator acoustic interaction transfers more sound power to higher harmonic frequency modes than to lower harmonic frequency modes.

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REFERENCES

1. Namba, M., Nakagawa, H. and Kubo, A., "Lifting surface theory to predict aerodynamic forces induced by oscillating blades under interaction of three bladeraws", *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 326(2009), pp. 599-622.
2. Namba, M., Nishino, R. and Ohgi, S. "Improved Hybrid Method of Predicting Fan Tone Noise", *Turbomachines: Aeroelasticity, Aeroacoustics, and Unsteady Aerodynamics*, Edited by V. Skivin, N. Saren, N. Savin and S. Frolov, Torus Press Ltd., September 2006, pp. 257-267. Proceedings of ISUAAAT 11(2006).

ANNEX A

OUTLINE OF THE UNSTEADY LIFTING SURFACE THEORY FOR THE ROTOR-STATOR INTERACTION NOISE

The interaction of the rotor wakes with the stator vanes and further acoustic interaction between the rotor and the stator bring about unsteady loadings of multiple frequency components on each blade rows. The unsteady loading on the m -th blade of each row is expressed by (see Ref. [2])

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rotor: } & \sum_{\substack{\mu=-\infty \\ \neq 0}}^{\infty} \Delta p_{R,\mu}(r, z_R) e^{i\omega_{R,\mu}t + i2\pi\sigma_{R,\mu}m/N_R}, \\ \text{Stator: } & \sum_{\substack{\mu=-\infty \\ \neq 0}}^{\infty} \Delta p_{S,\mu}(r, z_S) e^{i\omega_{S,\mu}t + i2\pi\sigma_{S,\mu}m/N_S}, \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Here, the frequencies and the numbers of nodal diameters are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_{R,\mu} &= -\mu N_S \Omega, \quad \sigma_{R,\mu} = \mu N_S : \mu = \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots \\ \omega_{S,\mu} &= \mu N_R \Omega, \quad \sigma_{S,\mu} = \mu N_R : \mu = \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Further, z_S and z_R denote local axial coordinates for the stator and the rotor, respectively.

The unsteady loadings under rotor-stator acoustic interaction are determined by the following simultaneous integral equations resulting from the flow tangency conditions on the blade and vane surfaces (Ref. [1]):

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_h^1 \int_{-C_{aR}/2}^{C_{aR}/2} \Delta p_{R,\nu}(\rho, \zeta) K_{q\perp}(r, 0, z_R - \zeta | \rho; N_R, \Omega, \omega_{R,\nu}, \sigma_{R,\nu}) d\zeta d\rho \\ & + \sum_{\mu=-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i(\mu N_R + \sigma_{R,\nu})\Omega z_R} \int_h^1 \int_{-C_{aS}/2}^{C_{aS}/2} \Delta p_{S,\mu}(\rho, \zeta) K_{q\perp R-S}^{(\nu)}(r, z_R - G - \zeta | \rho; N_S, 0, \omega_{S,\mu}, \sigma_{S,\mu}) d\zeta d\rho \\ & = 0 : \quad -\frac{C_{aR}}{2} \leq z_R \leq \frac{C_{aR}}{2}, \\ & \quad \nu = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_h^1 \int_{-C_{aS}/2}^{C_{aS}/2} \Delta p_{S,\nu}(\rho, \zeta) K_{q\perp}(r, 0, z - \zeta | \rho; N_S, 0, \omega_{S,\nu}, \sigma_{S,\nu}) d\zeta d\rho \\ & + \sum_{\mu=-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-i(\mu N_S + \sigma_{S,\nu})\Omega(z+G)} \int_h^1 \int_{-C_{aR}/2}^{C_{aR}/2} \Delta p_{R,\mu}(\rho, \zeta) K_{q\perp S-R}^{(\nu)}(r, z + G - \zeta | \rho; N_R, \Omega, \omega_{R,\mu}, \sigma_{R,\mu}) d\zeta d\rho \\ & = W_{\perp S,\nu}(r, z) : \quad -\frac{C_{aS}}{2} \leq z \leq \frac{C_{aS}}{2}, \\ & \quad \nu = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Here, $W_{\perp S,\nu}(r, z)$ denotes the upwash velocity of the oncoming rotor wakes on the stator vanes composed of Fourier components of circumferential wave number $\nu N_R : \nu = \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$

The second terms on the left hand side of Eqs. (17) and (18) represent the acoustic interaction between the two blade rows. Each kernel function $K_{q\perp R-S}^{(\nu)}$ or $K_{q\perp S-R}^{(\nu)}$ involved in the terms is of a simple sinusoidal dependence on G . However, we should note that all frequency components (μ) of the stator vane loadings contribute to each frequency component (ν) of the rotor blade loadings in Eq. (17), whereas all frequency components (μ) of the rotor blade loadings contribute to each frequency component (ν) of the stator vane loadings in Eq. (18).

Here, special mention will deserve to be made of numerical methods of solving system equations (17) and (18). If a very high computation cost is necessary, the theoretical method can not be of great advantage over CFD. Main difficulties come from the fact that kernel functions are composed of Bessel function series expansion, which are of nonuniform convergence. Computation of convolution of kernel function and loading function in high accuracy is the key to obtain reliable numerical results. The author developed a special technique to cope with the problem, description of which is given in e.g., Ref. [1]. Owing to the technique, the numerical results shown in Figs. 8 and 9, for instance, can be obtainable in a few minutes on a modern personal computer.

From the stand points of the acoustics, the rotor blades and the stator vanes are sound sources of pressure dipoles, and the generated sound pressure field in the duct frame of reference can be expressed by

$$\begin{aligned}
p = & \sum_{\nu=-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i\nu N_R \Omega t} \sum_{\mu=-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i(\nu N_R + \mu N_S)(\theta - \Omega z)} \int_h^1 d\rho \int_{-c_{aR}/2}^{c_{aR}/2} \Delta p_{R,\mu}(\rho, \zeta) \\
& \times K_p^{(\nu)}(r, z - \zeta \mid \rho; N_R, \Omega, \omega_{R,\mu}, \sigma_{R,\mu}) d\zeta \\
& + \sum_{\substack{\mu=-\infty \\ \neq 0}}^{\infty} e^{i\mu N_R \Omega t} \sum_{\nu=-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i(\nu N_S + \mu N_R)\theta} \int_h^1 d\rho \int_{-c_{aS}/2}^{c_{aS}/2} \Delta p_{S,\mu}(\rho, \zeta) \\
& \times K_p^{(\nu)}(r, z - G - \zeta \mid \rho; N_S, 0, \omega_{S,\mu}, \sigma_{S,\mu}) d\zeta
\end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

It is convenient to express the sound field as composed of the duct modes of circumferential wave number n and radial mode number ℓ , and we express the sound fields upstream from the rotor (subscript $-$) and downstream from the stator (subscript $+$) by

$$p_{\pm}(r, \theta, z, t) = \sum_{\nu=-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i\nu N_R \Omega t} \sum_{\mu=-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i n \theta} \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} R_{\ell}^{(n)}(r) e^{i \alpha_{\ell, \pm}^{(n)} z} FP_{\pm}(\nu, \mu, \ell), \tag{20}$$

$$n = \nu N_R + \mu N_S, \tag{21}$$

$$\alpha_{\ell, \pm}^{(n)} = \nu N_R \Omega M_a^2 / (1 - M_a^2) \mp \Lambda_{\ell}^{(n)} / i,$$

$$\Lambda_{\ell}^{(n)} = \begin{cases} \sqrt{B} & : B > 0 : \text{cut-off mode} \\ i \operatorname{sgn}(\nu N_R \Omega) \sqrt{-B} & : B < 0 : \text{cut-on mode} \end{cases}, \tag{22}$$

$$B = \left\{ (k_{\ell}^{(n)})^2 - (\nu N_R \Omega)^2 M_a^2 / (1 - M_a^2) \right\} / (1 - M_a^2)$$

Here, $R_{\ell}^{(n)}(r)$ and $k_{\ell}^{(n)}$ denote the radial eigenfunction and the radial eigenvalue, respectively. Since the circumferential wave number $n = \nu N_R + \mu N_S$ is dependent on two integral parameters ν and μ , we identify the complex modal pressure amplitude $FP_{\pm}(\nu, \mu, \ell)$ by three integral parameters ν , μ and ℓ . Note that the modal pressure amplitudes are essentially dependent on the unsteady loadings on the blades and the vanes.

Finally, the modal acoustic powers are given by

$$EM_{\pm}(\nu, \mu, \ell) = \frac{\pi (1 - M_a^2) |\nu N_R \Omega| |\Lambda_{\ell}^{(n)}|}{\left\{ |\nu N_R \Omega| / (1 - M_a^2) \mp |\Lambda_{\ell}^{(n)}| \right\}^2} |FP_{\pm}(\nu, \mu, \ell)|^2 \tag{23}$$

We define the acoustic power of circumferential wave number component $EC_{\pm}(\nu, \mu)$ and frequency component $E_{\pm}(\nu)$ by

$$EC_{\pm}(\nu, \mu) = \sum_{\ell} EM_{\pm}(\nu, \mu, \ell) \tag{24}$$

$$E_{\pm}(\nu) = \sum_{\mu} \sum_{\ell} EM_{\pm}(\nu, \mu, \ell) \tag{25}$$

Note that the acoustic powers are contributed by the cut-on duct modes only. Therefore, summations in Eqs. (24) and (25) are applied only for cut-on modes.